

The Function of Br_2^- and I_2^- Ions and the Influence of Cl^- Ions in some Oxidation Reactions in Light.

BY R. M. PURKAYASTHA.

The interaction between organic acids and bromine in light and in darkness have recently been investigated (Ghosh and Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 165; Ghosh and Basu, *ibid.*, 1928, 5, 343.; Purkayastha, *ibid.*, 1929, 6, 376, 385; Ghosh and Purkayastha, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, B7, 276, 285). In absence of a bromide and with an excess of mandelic or phenyllactic acid the reactions were bimolecular in the dark and unimolecular in light (Purkayastha, *loc. cit.*). When a bromide was present in excess, the dark and light reactions were unimolecular and zero-molecular respectively. The velocity constants in both cases diminished with the concentration of the bromide. It was suggested that in light the active bromine atoms and in the dark the activated bromine molecules were responsible for starting the chain of reactions (Ghosh and Purkayastha, *loc. cit.*).

In absence of a bromide the velocity for the dark reaction is given by

$$-d\frac{[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = \frac{k'[\text{Br}_2 \text{ free}]^2 [\text{A}']}{k''[\text{Br}_2 \text{ initial}]^2 + 1} \quad \dots (1)$$

When the bromide, a powerful inhibitor, is present in excess the chain length is considerably shortened and the velocity is given by

$$-d\frac{[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = k[\text{Br}_2 \text{ total}] [\text{A}'] \left[\frac{k_1}{\text{Br}} + 1 \right] \quad \dots (2)$$

For the light reactions in absence and in presence of an excess of bromide we get respectively,

$$\frac{-d[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = \sqrt{kI} [\text{A}'] \cdot \frac{k_s [\text{Br}_2]}{k_s [\text{Br}_2 \text{ initial}]^2 + k_s} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{-d[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = \sqrt{kI} [\text{A}'] \left[\frac{k_1}{\text{Br}} + 1 \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

where $[A']$ is the concentration of the anion of the reacting organic acid and $[Br']$ concentration of bromine ion.

With an excess of reacting acid equation (4) shows that the reaction becomes zeromolecular.

Zeromolecular constants should also be obtained for radiations which can effect the decomposition of bromine molecules into atoms. This has been experimentally realised. Quite good zeromolecular constants were obtained for the wave-lengths (given in microns) 542, 488, 448, 408, and 365. Some of the results are given below.

TABLE I.

Wave-length = 542 $\mu\mu$.		Temp. = 30°.				
·31 M-Mandelic acid;		·127 M-KBr;		·0155 M-Br ₂ .		
Time in minutes	...	0	45	90	140	205
(a-x)	...	12.5	11.6	10.75	9.5	8.1
x/t	...		·020	·019	·021	·021

TABLE II.

Wave-length = 366 $\mu\mu$.		Temp. = 30°.				
·38 M-Lactic acid;		·192 M-KBr;		·0226 M-Br ₂ .		
Time in minutes	...	0	30	60	90	120
(a-x)	...	19.05	18.15	17.25	16.3	15.35
x/t	...		·030	·030	·0316	·0316

TABLE III.

Wave-length = 448 $\mu\mu$.		Temp = 30°.		
·34 M-Lactic acid.				
KBr Conc.	Br. Conc.	Total Br, conc. in μ . mol.	x/t .	$x t / \frac{h_1}{Br} + 1$.
·2	·15	·03	·0383	81 × 10 ⁻⁴
·133	·1039	·0187	·054	31 × ..
·0633	·067	·0117	·083	31 × ..
·1	·08	·015	·064	29 × ..
·0833	·067	·0071	·082	31 × ..
·125	·0973	·0107	·058	31 × ..
·167	·127	·0144	·045	31 × ..
·075	·062	·0107	·078	28 × ..
·208	·156	·0189	·084	29 × ..

Similar results were also obtained with mandelic acid.

TABLE IV.

Influence of Thickness of Reaction Layer.

Acid conc.	Mean wave-length ($\mu\mu$).	Inverse ratio of the thickness of reaction layers.	Ratio of velocity constants.
.192 M-KBr; (Mandelic acid)	390	2	1.7
	408	2	1.54
	488	2	1.16
.33M (Lactic acid)	390	2	1.65
	408	2	1.54
	488	2	1.15

The reaction cells were .5 cm. and 1 cm. thick respectively. For complete absorption of light the velocity constants should vary as the inverse ratio of the thickness of the reaction layers. The above results show that at $488\mu\mu$ the ratio of the velocity constants is only 1.15 or the light absorption is far from complete whereas at $390\mu\mu$ the ratio is 1.7 and the absorption is very strong.

Influence of Cl^- ions on the Photochemical Oxidation by Bromine.

The oxidation of several hydroxy acids by bromine was shown to be strongly accelerated by the presence of chlorine ions. The acceleration was observed to be nearly proportional to the concentration of chlorine ions. Ghosh and Purkayastha (*loc. cit.*) attributed it to the activation of bromine molecules by collision with chlorine ions.

The results given in Table V show that instead of an acceleration, the light reactions are appreciably retarded by the presence of chlorine ions. The energy of activation of a bromine molecule is no doubt less than that for its dissociation into atoms and while bromine molecules may become activated by collision with chlorine ions, the active bromine atoms may suffer deactivation on collision with them. It has also been found that the retardation increases with the concentration of chlorine ions.

In all cases however where a bromide is present, the dark reactions are unimolecular but the light reactions are zero-molecular.

The reaction between phenyllactic acid and bromine gives nearly unimolecular constants on account of the fact that the dark reaction

is considerable. Thus in presence of $\cdot 222M$ -KCl the unimolecular constant for the thermal reaction is $\cdot 0033$ and for the photochemical reaction, $\cdot 00484$. The last column in Table V contains the velocity constants due to light only.

TABLE V.

	Blue light.	Temp. = 26° .
$\cdot 0522M$ -Br ;	$\cdot 0116M$ -HBr ;	$\cdot 0844M$ -Br ₂ .
Acid conc.	KCl Conc.	k_0 (zeromolecular).
$\cdot 278M$ (Mandelic)	0 $\cdot 0555$ $\cdot 222$	$\cdot 094$ $\cdot 091$ $\cdot 087$
$\cdot 276M$ (Lactic)	0 $\cdot 222$	$\cdot 087$ $\cdot 080$
		k (unimolecular).
$\cdot 0833M$ (Phenyllactic)	0 $\cdot 0555$ $\cdot 222$	$\cdot 00187$ $\cdot 00171$ $\cdot 00154$

The Function of I_3^- ions in Photochemical Oxidation by Iodine.

Since iodine forms I_3^- ions in presence of a soluble iodide a similar mechanism of the oxidation by iodine may be expected. Oxidation of sodium salts of organic acids by iodine in presence of potassium iodide has been studied by Dhar and others (*J. Phys Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1308 ; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 451, 473). The reactions were found to be either unimolecular or semimolecular. It appears from their data that unimolecular constants are obtained in those instances in which the light reaction proceeds very slowly (about 5 to 10%) in comparison to that in the dark, for instance, sodium lactate and iodine, sodium tartrate and iodine; whereas semimolecular constants are obtained in the reactions between sodium citrate, sodium formate, sodium malate and iodine in which the rate of the dark reaction is quite comparable to that of the light reaction. It should be noted that the dark reactions are in all cases unimolecular. It is evident that in the first group, even if the light reaction be of a different order, the combined light and thermal reaction will very nearly conform to the order of the dark reaction but in the second group the observed order of the reaction will be

intermediate between the orders of the light and dark reactions, on the assumption that the light reaction is zeromolecular and a semimolecular constant is naturally expected. Dhar and Mukerji (*J. Phys. Chem., loc. cit.*) give the following values for the combined light and thermal effects for the reaction between sodium formate and iodine. The first three columns in Table VI and VII contain their results.

TABLE VI.

White light. Temp. = 30°.

·156N-Sodium formate ; ·0084N-Iodine ; ·031N-Potassium
iodide ; ·137N-Sodium acetate.

Time in minutes.	Combined light and thermal reaction [$a - (x_1 + x_2)$].	k_1 (Semi- molecular).	k_1 Amount of change due to dark reaction in each suc- cessive interval as calculated from unimolecular const. $k_1 = \cdot 01$.	k_2 Amount of change due to light reaction in each suc- cessive inter- val.	k_0 (Zero-mole- cular).
0	3.55	—	—	—	—
9	2.8	·0528	·65	·2	·022
15.5	2.24	·059	·39	·17	·026
24.5	1.5	·0557	·44	·3	[·033]
30	1.2	·0544	·18	·12	·023
38	·8	·0533	·2	·2	·025

TABLE VII. (Higher intensity).

0	3.55	—	—	—	—
8	2.8	·0600	·61	·24	·030
15	2.1	·0611	·42	·28	·040
22	1.55	·0605	·32	·24	·034
30	1	·0607	·26	·29	·036

Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 781) finds the velocity constant k_1 for the dark reaction to be ·00556 at 25° and 3.89 as the temperature coefficient. The concentrations of sodium formate, iodine and potassium iodide were ·1667N, ·0088N, and ·034N respectively. The concentrations of the reacting substances are nearly the same in

both cases. The velocity constant for the dark reaction will be nearly .01 at 90°. The amount of change in successive intervals due to the thermal reaction has been calculated from the expression

$$k' = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{(a-x)}$$
 with this value of k_1 . Appreciable variation in

the value of k_1 will not materially alter the nature of the results. It will of course affect the absolute values obtained. The results given in Tables VI and VII make it clear that the light reactions are truly zeromolecular. The semimolecular constants obtained by Dhar is to be attributed to the combined light and thermal effects.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

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